

A technique for charge density measurement in laser-cluster interaction studies[†]

S. Das^a, P. Sharma^a, A. Majumder^b and R. K. Vatsa^{a*}

^aChemistry Division, ^bLaser and Plasma Technology Division,
Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, Mumbai-400 085, India

E-mail : rkvatsa@barc.gov.in

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Abstract : Ethyl bromide clusters have been irradiated with 532 nm laser pulses at gigawatt intensity condition. The time-of-flight mass spectra consist of multiply charged atomic ions of carbon and bromine along with mono-positively charged molecular and cluster fragments. To determine the charge density associated with the laser-cluster interaction, a new and simple technique has been devised for the time-of-flight configuration. In the new configuration, repeller grid has been changed to a thin plate and the electrical biasing arrangement has been modified. This new configuration allows measurement of charge densities as well as time-of-flight mass spectra without disturbing the experimental arrangement.

Keywords : Laser-cluster interaction, charge density, time-of-flight mass spectrometer (TOFMS), Coulomb explosion.

Introduction

Clusters are defined as aggregates of atoms/molecules which represent a bridge between a molecular and bulk description of matter, which are held by weak interactions like van der Waals forces. Because of its high local electron density, the coupling of optical field of laser light with cluster is extremely efficient. Over the last two decades, laser-cluster interaction has been studied extensively because of its wide application in intense pulsed X-ray production, table top accelerators and high energy physics¹⁻⁵. Huge energy deposition per molecule⁶ in a cluster results in its severe ionization leaving positively charged ions in close proximity to each other. The immense Coulomb repulsion between similar charges leads to violent breakup of the charged matter along with the emission of energetic particles and photons¹. This phenomenon is known as Coulomb explosion and it constitutes one of the significant events in laser-cluster interaction. Coulomb explosion of atomic and molecular clusters employing laser pulses in the intensity range of 10^{14} – 10^{20} W/cm² has been reported over a wide range of electromagnetic spectrum from IR to X-ray region in different types of systems such as rare gas, molecular, ionic and metal cluster⁷⁻¹¹.

Recently, the occurrence of Coulomb explosion was very surprisingly reported using nanosecond laser pulses of intensity $\sim 10^9$ W/cm² in clusters of methyl iodide^{12,13}, carbon disulfide¹⁴, acetone¹⁵ etc. These studies highlighted salient features of the interaction such as existence of highly charged ions, large kinetic energy of the ions, role of cluster size, effect of laser wavelength, polarization and intensity. But the mechanism of efficient energy coupling between laser field and cluster is still not understood. Li and co-workers^{13,17} proposed a three-stage model which assumes that the nanosecond laser-induced Coulomb explosion of cluster is initiated by multi-photon ionization (MPI) of the constituent molecules within the neutral clusters. Subsequently some of the ionized electrons, which still continue to form integral part of ionized cluster (i.e. caged electrons), extract energy from the laser field via inverse bremsstrahlung (IBS) process i.e. absorption of energy from the electromagnetic laser field on collision with neutral and ionic species within the cluster. Once these caged electrons gain enough energy to surpass the corresponding ionization potential of ion, multiple ionization process may start via stepwise electron impact ionization, resulting in generation of multiply ionized species within the cluster. Finally, these multi-

[†]In honour of Professor Jai P. Mittal.

ply ionized clusters, which are in close proximity, undergo Coulomb explosion due to huge electrostatic repulsion resulting in generation of multiply charged atomic ions with large kinetic energies. This model comprising of 'multi-photon ionization ignited-inverse bremsstrahlung heating electron impact ionization' has been used to explain different facets of Coulomb explosion phenomenon occurring on interaction of molecular clusters with nanosecond laser pulses with intensity $\sim 10^9\text{--}10^{11}$ W/cm².

In this context, the concept of nano-plasma has been evoked which might be playing a crucial role in energy absorption mechanism in nanosecond laser induced Coulomb explosion. To investigate whether plasma is involved in the process, the first parameter to be experimentally measured is charge density. In the present work, ethyl bromide clusters were used as a test system and irradiated with laser light at 532 nm under laser intensity $\sim 5 \times 10^9$ W/cm². In order to get the charge density of the interaction region, the repeller grid was changed to a thin plate and the electrical biasing arrangement of the time-of-flight mass spectrometer (TOF-MS) was modified, thus

allowing measurement of TOF-MS and charge densities under identical conditions.

Experimental

Experiments were done in the indigenously designed and fabricated TOF-MS and a schematic of the set up is given in Fig. 1 along with the photograph of the instrument (Fig. 2)¹⁶. Basic components of the experimental setup can be classified into three parts namely molecular beam, laser beam and TOF-MS which are mutually orthogonal to each other. The TOF-MS consists of three interconnected chambers i.e. expansion chamber, ionization chamber and time-of-flight tube, which are differentially pumped to attain the vacuum of 2×10^{-6} Torr. These have been described below in greater detail.

(a) Molecular beam arrangement :

The molecular beam of the volatile liquid sample was produced by bubbling inert carrier gas (He) through the sample and allowing the mixture to expand through the pulsed valve nozzle of diameter 0.8 mm. The valve driver is able to operate the nozzle either internally or externally triggered with pulse duration between 160 to 500

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the experimental setup for laser-cluster interaction.

Fig. 2. Photograph of the TOF-MS fabricated in Chemistry Division, BARC.

μs at variable repetition rate. The pressure of the carrier inert gas was varied between 1–5 atm to optimize ion signal. The supersonic jet so produced from pulsed valve was skimmed at a distance of 5 cm from the pulsed nozzle. This distance is sufficient for the clustering process to be over. The distance between the skimmer and the interaction region was 17 cm. One additional aperture of 3 mm diameter was introduced in the path of molecular beam, 5 cm before the interaction zone in order to define the volume of the interaction region. Generally, the pulse valve gives a distribution of cluster size and the average cluster size is guided by the inert gas pressure, temperature of the stagnation chamber, diameter of the nozzle and the bond constant of the clustering molecule. Thereby, “Hagena parameter” is widely used to determine the average size of pure cluster under given set of experimental conditions. The gas pulse would take some time in travelling from valve to interaction region and the time delay between the laser pulse and the pulsed valve were adjusted in such a way so that the laser will interact with the most clustered region of the gas pulse. For adjusting the delay between the two pulses, a digital delay generator has been employed which takes care of the synchronous interaction of molecular beam with laser beam. By changing the delay time, one can choose the laser pulse to hit the least clustered portion or the most clustered portion of the gas pulse.

(b) Laser beam arrangement :

Ionization of the molecular beam has been carried out by commercially available pulsed Nd : YAG nanosecond laser (Quanta system, GIANT G790-10) which can provide fundamental (1064 nm) as well as second (532 nm), third (355 nm) and fourth (266 nm) harmonic. For 532 nm, the duration of the laser pulses was measured in oscilloscope using a photodiode and it was about 9 ns. The laser beam was steered to the ionization chamber using four mirrors and the energy of the pulses before entering the ionization chamber was ~ 10 mJ. The laser light was mildly focused at the interaction region through a lens placed outside the ionization chamber having a focal length of 35 cm.

During the course of experiments, the laser spot size at the interaction region was measured by putting a thin strip of copper foil and allowing the laser light to fall on it. The focused laser beam where the intensity is high drills a hole in the copper foil after ~ 200 shots. Five such holes were taken at different position of the copper foil and measured under Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and the average diameter of the laser spot was $\sim (175 \pm 10) \mu\text{m}$. The intensity at the interaction region turns out to be $\sim 5 \times 10^9 \text{ W/cm}^2$ for this spot size and the area of the interaction region was taken to be 3 mm

long cylinder (as defined by the aperture) with $\sim 175 \pm 10 \mu\text{m}$ diameters. Fig. 3 is a representative SEM picture of the laser spot at the interaction region.

Fig. 3. SEM picture of the laser spot at the interaction region.

(c) *Time-of-flight arrangement* :

The dual acceleration stage TOF-MS set-up consist of three grids namely, repeller (R), extractor (E) and accelerator (A) in which interaction region lies between the R and E (Fig. 1). The R and E grids were 20 mm apart while E and A grids were separated by 10 mm distance. When positively charged ions were produced due to multiphoton ionization of the molecular beam by laser light of intensity 10^9 W/cm^2 , they were pushed towards the detector assembly by applying a positive voltage gradient which was generated by applying 3000 V at R grid and 2000 V at E grid and 0 V at A. The field between interaction region and E grid constitutes the extraction field while acceleration field is applied between E and A grid. For proper focusing of the ions at the detector, Wiley-McLaren condition has been achieved by adjusting the voltages of R and E grids according to the laser spot position. To improve the ion collection efficiency, two sets of parallel plates were placed at vertical and horizontal position respectively and by applying small voltages, few tens of volts, the ions were directed towards the entrance hole of the Einzel lens (En). Einzel lens is an assembly of three stainless steel discs of 10 mm thickness having 20 mm holes at the centre. The voltages on these three discs were 0-V-0 and by varying V the ions can be focused on to the detector. Once the ions reach the field

free flight tube, they would move according to its m/z ratio and reach the detector at different times. The flight tube is about 100 cm in length. The resolution of the mass spectrometer is ~ 300 . At the end of the flight tube, Channel Electron Multiplier (CEM) detector was placed for detection of charged particles and typically -2500 V was applied for getting a reasonably good signal. The output of the detector was fed to the oscilloscope through a fast pre-amplifier and the oscilloscope was triggered in the external mode by the output pulse from a photodiode placed near the laser beam path.

(d) *Charge measurement arrangement* :

The basic TOF-MS set-up remains same in the new arrangement. Since we wanted to observe the mass spectra of the clusters and record the number of charges produced under identical experimental condition, the ion optics was modified in such a way so that the TOF remains unaffected and only voltages are either changed or switched off. Hence the R grid was replaced by thin copper plate. In order to measure the number of charges associated with interaction region, R was connected to the oscilloscope across a variable resistor (Fig. 4). During these experiments, a positive potential was applied to E grid to push all the positively charged ions produced due to ionization of the molecular beam towards the copper plate and were collected at the R plate. The current produced in the circuit due to the ions and electrons was recorded in the form of voltage by applying appropriate resistor parallel to the oscilloscope. The applied resistance was varied to improve the signal/noise ratio without losing the time information of the data.

In the present work, ethyl bromide clusters were irradiated with 532 nm laser pulses having an intensity of $\sim 5 \times 10^9 \text{ W/cm}^2$. The pulsed valve opening time was kept 300 μs and the delay between the laser pulse and the gas pulse was varied in order to interact either with the most clustered portion or with the least clustered portion of the gas pulse. The inert carrier gas (He) back up pressure was optimized at 2 atm. The electrical connections are schematically shown in Figs. 4(a) and 4(b) for time-of-flight arrangement and charge density measurement respectively. For charge measurement experiment, 2000 V was applied to the E grid and signal was collected from R plate through a 3.3 k Ω load resistor.

Fig. 4. Schematic of the electrical connection of TOF and charge density measurement.

Results and discussion

Fig. 5 represents the time-of-flight mass spectra of ethyl bromide clusters subjected to 532 nm at $\sim 5 \times 10^9$ W/cm² intensity condition. From the spectra, it is clear that it consists of singly charged fragments of ethyl bromide molecule as well as multiply charged atomic ions of carbon (up to C⁴⁺) and bromine (up to Br⁵⁺). The fragments were H⁺, C⁺, CH₃⁺, C₂⁺, C₂H₅⁺, Br⁺, CBr⁺, C₂H₅Br⁺ at m/z 1, 12, 15, 24, 29, (79, 81), (91, 93), (108, 110) respectively obtained due to multi-photon ionization of ethyl bromide. From the spectra it is very clear that all the charged states of bromine show double peaks due to two different isotopes. Presence of molecular ion peak at 108 and 110 indicates that the photochemical process undergo ionization followed by dissociation suggestive of a ladder climbing mechanism at this wavelength. The mass peak at m/z at 137, 139 (see the inset of Fig. 5) is a signature of cluster fragment which has been formed due to dissociation of bromine atom from dimer cation of ethyl bromide. Therefore, dimer formation is evident from the spectra but it difficult to estimate the number of monomer present in the cluster before it undergoes intense

fragmentation. However, in our earlier studies (CH₃I)_n (n = number of monomer present in a cluster) under similar experimental condition was investigated and fragments of hexamer (n = 6) could be observed¹². The mass peak at m/z 18 occurs due to moisture present in the ethyl bromide sample and as a consequence Coulomb exploded doubly charged oxygen ion (O²⁺) was observed at m/z = 8. Formation of Br⁵⁺ and C⁴⁺ requires 59.7 eV and 64.5 eV respectively which implies at least 26 photons of 532 nm (2.33 eV) needs to be absorbed coherently which is quite improbable at this laser intensity. Therefore there must be some efficient mechanism other than multi-photon ionization which is operating under these conditions.

Fig. 6a depicts the ion signal obtained from the oscilloscope recorded with 3.3 k Ω resistance during charge measurement experiment. An extraction field of 2000 V was applied to E grid in order to collect maximum number of ions. The area under the curve gives the measure of the number of charges involved in the process.

Total charge (Q_{Total}) = Area under the curve (V sec)/ (Value of single charge (1.6×10^{-19} Coulomb) \times Applied resistance (3.3 k Ω).

Fig. 5. Time-of-flight mass spectra of ethyl bromide cluster at 532 nm under laser intensity 10^9 W/cm².

Fig. 6. The ion signal obtained from the oscilloscope during charge density measurement.

In this case the area under the curve turns out $\sim 2.8 \times 10^{-8}$ V sec. Therefore, the number of charges (Q_{Total}) associated with interaction zone is 5.3×10^7 .

In order to determine the charge density, the volume of the interaction zone must be known accurately. The interaction region as defined by the aperture was 3 mm long cylinder with (175 ± 10) μm diameter (as described in Experimental section). Therefore the charge density (n_i) of the interaction zone becomes 7.4×10^{11} per cm^3 .

Charge density (n_i) = Number of charges (5.3×10^7)/Volume of interaction zone (7.2×10^{-5} cm^3)

Previously, it has been observed that nanosecond laser induced Coulomb explosion depends on cluster size¹⁵ and occurs predominantly in most clustered region. But there was no signature of Coulomb explosion when least clustered region was irradiated under identical conditions. Therefore, it is interesting to measure the charge density associated with the least clustered region and compare it with the most clustered region. Under the same set of experimental conditions, when the delay between laser pulse and the gas pulse has been changed so that the laser pulse now interacts with the least clustered region, no detectable ion signal could be obtained (as shown in Fig. 6b). In the present set up, the resistance could be varied up to a maximum value of 330 $\text{k}\Omega$ –1 $\text{M}\Omega$ but still no ion signal above base line could be observed under least clustered region. From this observation, it can be inferred that the charges associated with least clustered region is at least 100 to 300 times less than the most clustered region. In order to get the exact number of charges from the least clustered region, other more sensitive detector such as charge sensitive preamplifier will be employed in future experiments.

Conclusion

Ethyl bromide clusters ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{Br}$)_n have been irradiated with 532 nm nanosecond laser pulses of $\sim 5 \times 10^9$ W/cm^2 intensity. The time-of-flight mass spectrum shows Coulomb exploded multiply charged atomic species upto C^{4+} and Br^{5+} as well as singly charged fragments. In order to determine the charge density of the interaction region, a novel technique has been devised by minor modification of the ion optics and by changing the electrical bias arrangement of TOF-MS. The charge density

of ethyl bromide system under clustered conditions turns out to be 7.4×10^{11} per cm^3 . This data is very useful in order to determine the nature of the ion ensemble i.e. whether they are responding individually like single particle or have collective behavior as in plasma. However, to define ion assembly as plasma, other parameters like Debye length, plasma frequency needs to be calculated. In these calculations, electron temperature is one of the requirements which is unknown for this system under our experimental conditions. Our future studies are focused on determination of the experimental value of electron temperature so that the ion assembly can be characterized with relevant physical parameters.

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